

Guidelines on how to record and broadcast communities' meetings

M10 - Preliminary mock-ups for community governance

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Meeting broadcast - desktop mockup

How to Broadcast Community's meetings

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Creating a host

If not already present, it is necessary to create a host: this is the person who will broadcast the event through his/her mobile. In order to do that, from your PC click on [Manage Content](#) > [Hosts](#) > [Add +](#)

At this point, fill the form with your data:

Creating a Program

Now you can create your program. Click on [Go to program](#) and then on [Add +](#)

Now, fill the form.

The meeting: how it works in general

The telephone will broadcast the face to face dialogues but also the calls accepted/initiated by the host. The broadcasting will terminate either at the end of the duration of the program (set in advance) or when the host decides to hang up. In the next pages we will see what happens in detail.

At the preset time, the host will receive a call and will hear an automatic welcome message

Accepting or refusing the call

Host to press **1** to accept the call to broadcast the event. The host will hear a notification informing that he/she is being connected to the station. He/she will also hear a notification when connected to the station (after this he/she is on air and the mobile is a microphone!).

Host to press **2** to postpone the call to do the show (the station will hang up, you need to call it back to get on air)

After the host pressed 1 and went on air, he/she has these options:

a) Stand-by

Pressing "1": Both calls to him and the station will be terminated but if a caller calls into the program on a predetermined number, the host will receive a call and will be prompted if they are ready to get on air with the participant that called in.

b) Auto-answering mode

Pressing "3": Turn on/off automatic answering of calls from participants wishing to participate in the talk show.

In auto-answer mode, whenever a participant calls into the ongoing talk-show on a predetermined number, they automatically join the talk show as soon as their call is received.

c) Queuing mode

Pressing "4": Turn on/off queuing of calls from participants wishing to participate in the talk show.

In queuing mode, whenever a participant calls into the ongoing talk-show on a predetermined number, they will be added to a queue of participants who wish to participate on the show. Their call will be terminated by the station and their number placed on a list of people who can be called back to participate in the show.

In the event that someone calls in while queuing mode is enabled, the host will hear a notification informing them that they have a caller in the queue.

d) Call back

Pressing "5": Call back a participant who had earlier called in. A call will be initiated to the earliest registered number in the queue of interested participants.

e) Terminate the call

Pressing "6": terminate the call to a participant (either joined in auto answer mode, or called back).

f) Add a participant

Pressing "*": Manually add a number to the conference.

In the event that the host wishes to add a participant to the talk show by calling them, the host will then press * key, followed by the # key. They will then enter the number of the person they wish to call. The host then enters the number of the person they wish to call, including the country code (e.g 40, 351) and press the # key again to initiate the call. At this point the host will receive a notification informing them of the number that is being called. In the event that the call fails, the host will hear a notification informing them of the failure - otherwise the invitee is added to the conference. Example: During a call press *#40722123123# to call that number.

g) Terminate the call to the invited participant

Pressing "7": terminate the call to a participant invited and called using the "*" option.

h) Take a 5 minutes break

Pressing "9": Take a 5 min music break. The talk-show is suspended - the calls to the host and the station are both terminated. The host will be called back in 5 minutes.

SCENARIO 1: Host is ON air and adds 1 call(er)

- At the scheduled time, the host will receive an automatic call from the station and will hear a welcome message. He/she will press "1"
- The host press "3" to turn on the auto answer mode. Now the call-ins will automatically join the show (just one call at a time)
- The participant calls the station's number and, if the lines are open, he/she goes on air in the talk show with the host.
- The host press "6" to terminate the call to a participant. The show goes on.

SCENARIO 2: Host is ON air and adds more than 1 call(er)

- Host repeats steps 1-3 from Scenario 1 in order to have a live show with a caller/participant
- To manually add one person to the call, the host will press "*" followed by the phone number of the person and "#" to confirm. (* to cancel and repeat)
- If the person answers, station adds him/her to the show
- The host press "7" to terminate the call to the person. The show goes on.

SCENARIO 3: Host calls a listener in queue

- The host is on air and he/she is already chatting with a listener
- The host presses "4" to turn on queuing mode that allows him to record the numbers of the new people calling when the line is busy.
- A new listener calls: the call will be terminated by the station and the number placed on a list of people who can be called back. The host will hear a notification
- At the end of the first call, the host press "5" and a call will be initiated to the earliest registered number in the queue

SCENARIO 4: Host goes OFF air and a listener calls-in (in the program)

- At the scheduled time, the host will receive an automatic call from the station and will hear a welcome message. He/she will press "1"
- At some point he/she decides to go off air and press "1". The station plays a playlist/stream scheduled in parallel in advance
- A listener calls while the host is offline; the listener gets a voice prompt: "Please wait while we connect you to the station!"
- Station calls the host / plays voice prompt "You have a caller on the line. Press "1" to get connected to the station or "2" to ignore this call". The host presses 1 and goes on air with the listener